

COMPOSITE 3D-PRINTED PLATE-BASED MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS

Aya Hosoi^{1,2}, Jier Wang¹, Yuki Fujita^{1,2}, Tatsuo Tanaka³, Junichi Takahashi² and Ajit Panesar¹

¹Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London
Exhibition Road, SW7 2AZ, UK

Email: a.hosoi24@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <https://idea-lab-ic.github.io/#/>

² Asahi Kasei Corporation

1-3-1, Yakoh, Kawasaki-ku, Kawasaki-city, Kanagawa 210-0863, Japan

Email: second.author@m-tech.aau.dk, web page: <https://www.asahi-kasei.com/>

³Asahi Kasei Plastics Vietnam

703-704, 29 Le Duan, Ben Nghe Ward, 71000, Vietnam

web page: <https://www.asahi-kasei-plastics.com/en/>

Keywords: Computational modelling, Additive Manufacturing, Composites, Mechanical testing

ABSTRACT

Metamaterials have attracted interest in both academia and industry due to their outstanding properties across various fields, such as mechanical, thermal, electromagnetic and acoustic. Those properties are realised by underlying architectures of metamaterials. Controlling the micro-architecture in a multiscale metamaterial opens the possibility for multifunctional applications relevant to diverse sectors including aerospace, automotive, biomedical and sports.

Innovative metamaterial designs have been effectively derived from approaches such as inverse homogenisation and dehomogenisation, which have evolved from traditional density-based topology optimisation. Alternatives to these approaches, leveraging machine learning-based inverse generation strategies have also been developed. Our recent work has proposed a two-step metamaterial designing approach that combined topology optimisation and machine learning.

This study advances the proposed two-step approach by extending the geometry space to include 3D unit lattice cells and accommodating material anisotropy, specifically orthotropy in this study, opening the opportunity to utilise fibre-reinforced additive manufacturing. Numerical evaluation using finite element analysis confirmed that the optimal structures performed better than their uniformly designed counterparts, while the difference was marginal in isotropic materials due to the difference in boundary conditions applied in optimisation and numerical validation. The 3D extension was achieved by applying two types of unit lattice cells: truss-based BCC and plate-based BCC. The numerical evaluation showed that the plate-based BCC lattice structure outperformed the truss-based BCC, indicating the effectiveness of plate-based metamaterials.

This study aims to accelerate the development in the field of composite metamaterials by presenting the validated computational ML-based inverse design framework, considering practical fabrication and use cases. Future work will include the extension to other objective functions incorporating buckling, vibration, thermal etc. along with experimental validations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials (MMs) are intentionally designed architectures that exhibit effective properties surpassing those of their constituent materials. These properties range from electromagnetic to acoustic, thermal and mechanical characteristics, attracting researchers in various fields such as aerospace, automotive, biomedical and sports. [1] The properties of MMs are realised by their underlying micro-architectures, also known as unit lattice cells. Designing these lattice cells enables MMs to exhibit outstanding behaviours not found in nature.

A variety of lattice cell structures have been proposed as micro-architectures for MMs, such as truss-based, surface-based and plate-based lattices. Truss-based lattices are the most widely studied due to their geometric simplicity. Representative examples include Body-Centred Cubic (BCC) and Face-Centred Cubic (FCC) lattices, which are typically bending-dominated and thus relatively compliant at low volume fractions. Plate-based lattices, introduced by Berger et al. [2], are characterized by interconnected flat panels. Plate-based lattices have attracted interest because of their ability to approach the Hashin–Shtrikman (HS) bound, the theoretical limit of the elastic moduli in accordance with the volume fractions of isotropic lattices. Several research group have designed mechanical MMs utilising plate-based lattices. [3], [4]

Numerous approaches have been developed to effectively design the MMs' micro-architectures. For example, inverse homogenisation was proposed by utilising a density-based topology optimisation (TO) to minimise the error between the predefined target properties and the effective properties calculated by numerical homogenisation. [5] Dehomogenisation has been developed to concurrently optimise the macro and micro-architecture of MMs by parameterising pre-defined micro-architectures and applying homogenisation-based TO. [6], [7] As an alternative to these TO-based approaches, optimisation leveraging machine learning (ML) has gained interest as a computationally efficient approach. [8] Our recent study [9] has proposed a two-step designing approach for realising multi-scale architecture, i.e., lattice structure, by combining TO and ML. Various 2D lattice geometries considering isotropic material properties were explored. The lattice geometries were parameterised and optimised by a ML-based inverse generator to map architectures based on specified target properties.

This study advances on the proposed TO and ML-based lattice optimisation approach by extending the geometry space to include 3D unit lattice cells and considering material anisotropy, opening the opportunity to utilise fibre-reinforced additive manufacturing (FRAM). A FRAM material is simplified as a transversely isotropic, i.e., orthotropic, material in this study. The 3D lattice optimisation considers two types of 3D unit lattice cells: truss-based BCC and plate-based BCC. Finite element analysis (FEA) for a three-point bending (3PB) test is conducted to numerically evaluate the performance of the optimised lattice structures.

This study aims to accelerate the development in the field of composite metamaterials by presenting the validated computational ML-based inverse design framework, considering practical fabrication and use cases.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 TO and ML-based lattice optimisation

As described in Jier and Panesar (2022)[9], the lattice generation approach consists of two steps: 1) optimise mechanical property for each unit cell from density and stress distribution obtained by low resolution TO; 2) generate lattice unit cell to realise the optimal mechanical property using the ML-based inverse generator.

This study considered the Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB)-beam problem shown in Fig. 1. The objective of the lattice optimisation is to minimise the mechanical compliance C (a measure of the inverse of stiffness) defined as:

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the global stiffness matrix and \mathbf{U} is the global displacement vector. The optimisation starts with density-based low resolution TO described in Eqs. 2.

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\rho} C \\ s. t.: & \sum_{i=1}^N V_i \rho_i - V_f \leq 0 \\ & \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F} \\ & 0 \leq \rho_i \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of elements in the design domain, V_i is the elemental volume, ρ_i is the elemental density ($\rho_i = 1$ means that the element is filled with material while $\rho_i = 0$ means void), V_f is the volume fraction and \mathbf{F} is the global load vector. V_f was set to be as 0.5 in this study. Solid Isotropic Material Penalisation (SIMP) method is applied to calculate the elastic properties, i.e., Young's modulus, in each element by interpolating with the value of density ρ_i :

$$E(\rho_i) = E_{min} + E_0\rho_i^p \quad (3)$$

where E_{min} is the minimal value that the elemental Young's modulus can take ($E_{min} = 1.0 \times 10^{-9}$ in this study) and p is the penalisation factor in SIMP. In this study, p was set to be 2.6 in 2D cases based on the precious study [9] and 3 in 3D cases as a generalised value. As an example for the lattice optimisation, an optimal lattice structure having 20×10 unit cells (as Fig. 2b) is derived from the low resolution TO in 20×10 elements (as Fig. 2a).

Figure 1: The MBB-beam problem

Figure 2: Examples of (a) low resolution TO and (b) lattice structure for MBB-beam problem

2.1.1 Optimisation of mechanical property

This study applied elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{D} as a mechanical property to be optimised in the first step. Elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{D} represents the relationship between strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ as described in 2D and 3D in Eqs.4 and 5, respectively. The tensor in 2D and 3D has 6 and 21 independent entries because of its symmetry as shown in Eq. 6.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1111} & D_{1122} & D_{1112} \\ D_{2211} & D_{2222} & D_{2212} \\ D_{1211} & D_{1222} & D_{1212} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1111} & D_{1122} & D_{1133} & D_{1112} & D_{1123} & D_{1131} \\ D_{2211} & D_{2222} & D_{2233} & D_{2212} & D_{2223} & D_{2231} \\ D_{3311} & D_{3322} & D_{3333} & D_{3312} & D_{3323} & D_{3331} \\ D_{1211} & D_{1222} & D_{1233} & D_{1212} & D_{1223} & D_{1231} \\ D_{2311} & D_{2322} & D_{2333} & D_{2312} & D_{2323} & D_{2331} \\ D_{3111} & D_{3122} & D_{3133} & D_{3112} & D_{3123} & D_{3131} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \\ \varepsilon_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{31} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$D_{ijkl} = D_{klij} \quad (6)$$

The elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{D} in each low-resolution element is optimised based on the minimisation problem as in Eq. 7 so that the elemental mechanical compliance c_e be minimised.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{D}_e} c_e &= \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \mathbf{D}_e^{-1} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ \text{s. t. : } P(\mathbf{D}_e, v f_e) &\geq \epsilon \\ |v f_e - \rho_e(\text{SIMP})| &\leq \delta \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{D}_e is the elemental elastic tensor to be optimised, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is stress derived from the result of the low resolution TO, $P(\mathbf{D}_e, v f_e)$ is the probability of the combination of the values of \mathbf{D}_e and the lattice cell volume fraction $v f_e$, which are constrained by the elemental density from the low resolution TO ($\rho_e(\text{SIMP})$). ϵ and δ is the predefined limit of the probability and the volume fraction error.

2.1.2 Inverse generator for multi-scale lattice

This study advanced the previous study [9], which considered 2D truss-based BCC lattices, by extending unit cell types into 3D truss-based and plate-based BCC lattices. Each cell type was parameterised as shown in Fig. 3. 2D unit cells had 4 representative parameters, $a_1 - a_4$, while 3D unit cells had 8, $a_1 - a_8$. Based on the unit cell structure, a corresponding mechanical property, an effective elastic tensor \mathbf{D} described in 2.1.1, was calculated by applying numerical homogenization [10], [11]

Figure 3: Unit cells parameterisation for (a) 2D truss-based BCC, (b) 3D truss-based BCC and (c) 3D plate-based BCC

Based on the optimisation results of mechanical properties in 2.1.1, a corresponding structure of the lattice unit cell is obtained. This lattice unit cell generation is realised by a pretrained ML-based inverse generator. This study applied multi-layer perceptron (MLP) as a model utilised in the inverse generator. The input of the inverse generator is independent components of \mathbf{D}_e (6 components in 2D and 21 components in 3D) and the volume fraction $v f_e$. The output is a set of unit cell parameters ($r_1 - r_4$ in 2D and $r_1 - r_8$ in 3D). In the training processes, 5000 randomly generated sets of unit cell parameters along with computed volume fractions and numerically homogenised elastic tensors \mathbf{D} were applied as a training or testing data.

2.2 Materials and numerical validation

This study considered two materials, Nylon (Polyamide 6) and a short fibre-reinforced nylon called Onyx. The mechanical properties described in Table 1 were defined based on the datasheets by *Markforged Inc.* [12]. Onyx was assumed as isotropic material in 3D lattices as orthotropy in 3D was out of scope in this study.

The 2D lattice unit cell considering orthotropic material was divided into 4 regions, described as i-iv in fig. 5. Each region was assumed to have material properties specified in Table 2 by considering short fibre orientation in the printing process.

Material type	2D lattice		3D lattices
	Isotropic	Orthotropic	Isotropic
Mechanical properties used on optimisation process	$\rho = 1.1 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E = 1.7 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$	$\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E_{11} = 2.4 \text{ GPa}, E_{22} = 1.7 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3, G_{12} = E_{11}/2(1 + \nu)$	$\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E = 2.4 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$
Corresponding materials	Nylon (PA 6)	Onyx (PA with short CF)	Onyx (PA with short CF)

Table 1: Material properties

Figure 5: Assumption of material distribution in 2D unit cell with orthotropic material

Region in Figure 5	i	ii	iii	iv
Material type	Orthotropic	Orthotropic	Isotropic	Void
Fibre orientation (direction of E_{11})	45 deg	-45 deg	-	-
Mechanical properties	$\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E_{11} = 2.4 \text{ GPa}$ $E_{22} = 1.7 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$ $G_{xy} = E_{11}/2(1 + \nu)$		$\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E = 1.7 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu = 0.3$	$\rho = 0 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $E = 0 \text{ GPa}$

Table 2: Material properties in 2D unit cell with orthotropic material

Three-point bending (3PB) tests, which corresponds to the half MBB-beam problem, were simulated using finite element analysis (FEA) with *Abaqus CAE* based on the ASTM D7264/D7264M – 15 standard (Fig.4(b) [13]). All lattice structures were set to have the same size of $120 \times 30 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ as shown in Fig. 4(a). Flat plates with the thickness of 2mm were added where the specimens contacted the loading nose and the supports (middle of the top surface and the left and the right corner of the bottom surface). This is to smoothly load the specimens throughout the test as the contacting points change during the 3PB test. In this study, both materials, Nylon and Onyx were set as isotropic in the FEA validation for simplicity, though orthotropy in validation is to be considered in the future work.

Figure 4: Numerical validation (a) Sizing specification of the specimens, (b) Three-point bending test based on ASTM D7264/D7264M – 15 and (c) Corresponding FEA model

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 2D truss-based metamaterials

The application of the TO and ML-based lattice optimisation to 2D truss-based BCC using isotropic and orthotropic materials is detailed in Table 3. This table includes structural performance, i.e., mechanical compliance and mass, which is the volume fraction multiplied by material density. The number of unit cells were varied by changing the mesh resolution of low resolution TO.

Low resolution	Cell size	Material type	Lattice design	Compliance	Mass ($V_f \times \rho$)
20 × 10	30 × 30	Isotropic (Nylon)		59.8	$0.52 \times 1.1 = 0.57$
		Orthotropic (Onyx)		40.3	$0.46 \times 1.2 = 0.55$
8 × 4	30 × 30	Isotropic (Nylon)		202.6	$0.50 \times 1.1 = 0.55$
		Orthotropic (Onyx)		78.2	$0.48 \times 1.2 = 0.58$
6 × 3	30 × 30	Isotropic (Nylon)		319.7	$0.50 \times 1.1 = 0.55$
		Orthotropic (Onyx)		110.9	$0.48 \times 1.2 = 0.58$

Table 3: Optimisation results with isotropic and orthotropic materials in 2D truss-based BCC

The optimal structures having 6×3 lattice unit cells in Table 3 along with the uniform counterparts were extruded into the 2.5D structures as shown in the Fig.4(a) and numerically evaluated using FEA corresponding to the 3PB test, which are summarised in Table 4. The uniform counterparts had more widely distributed region having higher strain energy above the average while the optimal structures had higher values in specific regions (orange rectangles in the strain energy distribution in Table 4). This results in lower total strain energy, i.e., mechanical compliance, calculated by integrating the elemental strain energies. A stress-based constraint is needed to reduce stress in higher strain energy region in the optimal structures.

The specific stiffnesses, defined as a measure of the flexural stiffness of the structures, were higher in the optimal structures than in the uniform counterparts whereas the difference with Nylon was marginal. One of the reasons is considered to be a difference in boundary conditions used in the

optimisation (half MBB beam) and the FEA. Spatial positions of the supports were at the corner in the half MBB beam (Fig. 1) while at 10mm from the corners in the FEA (Fig. 4(b)). The assumption of the interaction between the lattice structures and the load / supports were also different; the half MBB beam applied fixed boundary condition while the FEA applied contact boundary condition. More investigation is needed for the boundary condition.

Material	Structure	Strain energy distribution at displacement 2mm	Specific stiffness N/mm (Load / displacement/ V_f)
Nylon	Uniform (benchmark)		162.5
	Optimal		165.1
Onyx	Uniform (benchmark)		229.4
	Optimal		335.6

Table 4: Maximum principal strain distribution of each structure

3.2 3D truss and plate-based metamaterials

Optimisation results with 3D lattices are summarised in Table 5. Unlike the truss-based BCC, plate-based BCC had less thickness variant structure because of its high surface area. Nevertheless, the thicker plates were seen in the cells connected to the load i.e., top left corner, and the support, i.e., bottom right corner. This was the same tendency as the 2D lattices in Table 3. The specific stiffness calculated from the FEA result was higher in the plate-based BCC than in the truss-based BCC, confirming the efficiency of the plate-based lattices in the same volume fraction. This result complies to the experimental work conducted by Tancogne-Dejean et al. [14], where the normalised Young's moduli of plate-based lattices surpassed those of truss-based lattices.

Low resolution	Cell type	Cell size	Lattice design	Specific stiffness N/mm (Load / displacement/ V_f)
$6 \times 3 \times 1$	Truss-based BCC	$30 \times 30 \times 30$		143.9
	Plate-based BCC	$50 \times 50 \times 50$		671.4

Table 5: Lattice optimisation results in 3D truss-based and lattice-based BCC

4 CONCLUSIONS

The TO and ML-based lattice optimisation approach was advanced to consider orthotropic material properties and 3D lattice structures. The optimal structures in both orthotropic and isotropic materials were numerically evaluated by computing 3PB test using FEA. The results showed that the optimal lattice structures were stiffer, i.e., had better performance, than their uniform counterparts while the difference was marginal in isotropic materials, possibly due to the difference in boundary conditions. The optimal structures had smaller regions having higher strain energy, resulting in the lower total strain energy, i.e., mechanical compliance.

The 3D lattice optimisation results considering truss-based BCC and plate-based BCC lattices showed a tendency for the graded lattice structures similar to those in 2D cases. The optimal plate-based BCC lattice structure had less-graded structures than the truss-based BCC due to its high surface area. The plate-based BCC lattice outperformed the truss-based BCC lattice, indicating the effectiveness of applying plate-based lattices in the proposed lattice optimisation approach.

This study presented a numerically validated TO and ML-based MM design framework to accelerate the development in the field of composite MMs. Future works will include the extension to other objective functions incorporating buckling, vibration, thermal etc. along with experimental validations.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Fan *et al.*, ‘A review of additive manufacturing of metamaterials and developing trends’, *Materials Today*, vol. 50, pp. 303–328, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.mattod.2021.04.019.
- [2] J. B. Berger, H. N. G. Wadley, and R. M. McMeeking, ‘Mechanical metamaterials at the theoretical limit of isotropic elastic stiffness’, *Nature*, vol. 543, no. 7646, pp. 533–537, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1038/nature21075.

- [3] B. Sun, X. Yan, P. Liu, Y. Xia, and L. Lu, 'Parametric plate lattices: Modeling and optimization of plate lattices with superior mechanical properties', *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 72, p. 103626, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.addma.2023.103626.
- [4] Y. Zhu, J. Pan, E. Polyzos, J. Wang, and L. Pyl, 'Design and numerical analysis of perforated plate lattice structures', *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 204, p. 112339, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.tws.2024.112339.
- [5] O. Sigmund, 'Materials with prescribed constitutive parameters: An inverse homogenization problem', *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 31, no. 17, pp. 2313–2329, Sep. 1994, doi: 10.1016/0020-7683(94)90154-6.
- [6] J. P. Groen and O. Sigmund, 'Homogenization-based topology optimization for high-resolution manufacturable microstructures', *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 113, no. 8, pp. 1148–1163, 2018, doi: 10.1002/nme.5575.
- [7] R. V. Woldseth, O. Sigmund, and P. D. L. Jensen, 'An 808 line phasor-based dehomogenisation Matlab code for multi-scale topology optimisation', *Struct Multidisc Optim*, vol. 67, no. 12, p. 205, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00158-024-03880-1.
- [8] D. Lee, W. (Wayne) Chen, L. Wang, Y.-C. Chan, and W. Chen, 'Data-Driven Design for Metamaterials and Multiscale Systems: A Review', *Advanced Materials*, vol. 36, no. 8, p. 2305254, 2024, doi: 10.1002/adma.202305254.
- [9] J. Wang and A. Panesar, 'Machine learning based lattice generation method derived from topology optimisation', *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 60, p. 103238, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.addma.2022.103238.
- [10] E. Andreassen and C. S. Andreasen, 'How to determine composite material properties using numerical homogenization', *Computational Materials Science*, vol. 83, pp. 488–495, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.commatsci.2013.09.006.
- [11] G. Dong, Y. Tang, and Y. F. Zhao, 'A 149 Line Homogenization Code for Three-Dimensional Cellular Materials Written in matlab', *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, vol. 141, no. 1, p. 011005, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1115/1.4040555.
- [12] 'Datasheets'. Accessed: Jun. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://markforged.com/datasheets>
- [13] 'Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials'. Accessed: Jun. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://store.astm.org/d7264_d7264m-15.html
- [14] T. Tancogne-Dejean, M. Diamantopoulou, M. B. Gorji, C. Bonatti, and D. Mohr, '3D Plate-Lattices: An Emerging Class of Low-Density Metamaterial Exhibiting Optimal Isotropic Stiffness', *Advanced Materials*, vol. 30, no. 45, p. 1803334, 2018, doi: 10.1002/adma.201803334.